

TYPES OF EUPHEMISMS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses the types of euphemisms . The facts show that the systematic study of euphemism as a whole as a speech layer, revealing all its speech-inner possibilities, describing its functional-methodological features, especially its relation to types of functional styles, is one of the most important and urgent problems of our methodology today. In general linguistics, euphemisms have been studied by many foreign and native linguists. The reason is that euphemisms have always been very actual in translation . It is crucial for translators and interpreters to know specific peculiarities of euphemisms, their types and functions. As it will remain actual for many years as languages are all the time in progress and new words appear in them and translators will be working on transferring them from one language into another.

Key words: euphemisms, avoidance, mitigation, rhetoric, abstraction, litotes, modification, slang, spin euphemisms, mispronunciation.

INTRODUCTION

“Euphemisms are unpleasant truths wearing diplomatic cologne” – Quentin Crisp. It is an indirect way of expressing something. While talking about sensitive subjects or something that might be rude, taboo or upsetting, euphemism is used to make things sound better and less offensive [6]. In some literatures it is written that euphemism is a polite expression used in place of words or phrases that might otherwise be considered harsh or unpleasant.

The use of euphemisms in language has been shaped as a historical and ethnographic phenomenon in connection with the taboo phenomenon. Euphemism

is associated with the development of traditions, cultural levels, aesthetic tastes, ethnic norms and many other aspects of society. As a language develops, so does its euphemistic layer. New forms of euphemism emerge on the basis of new morals and new worldviews.

Euphemisms are used for a variety of reasons, depending on the context and goal. Euphemisms are typically used in three situations– in times of mitigation, avoidance, and occasionally for rhetorical purposes [1].

First of all it is used for **avoidance**. Euphemisms are frequently used to avoid explicitly discussing things that could be considered bad or embarrassing, such as death, physical intercourse or excretory bodily processes. They can be made for good intentions or for sinister and cynical reasons, with the intent to deceive and confuse. For example, instead of saying that someone was fired, oftentimes, the phrase “let go” is used. Similarly, the term “passed away” is employed when discussing death [6].

Secondly, it is used as **mitigation**. Euphemisms are also employed to minimize, soften, or minimize the severity of large-scale injustices, war crimes, or other occurrences that require a pattern of avoidance in official comments or documentation. For example, when the government explains US economic decline, words like “recession” or “disinflation” are used instead of speaking literally. Similarly, euphemisms can be easily cited in ads, like when cars are not listed as “used” but rather “certified pre-owned” [7]

Thirdly, **rhetoric** function. Euphemism can also be used as a rhetorical device, often for aesthetic gain, again, to avoid harsher or more blunt terminology. It allows authors to speak about possibly taboo or embarrassing subjects without addressing them directly. When euphemism is used as a rhetorical device, the purpose is to shift the valence of a description.

There are several groups of euphemisms in English. The most common types of euphemism used in writing are :

1. Abstraction: Some euphemisms serve to distance people from unpleasant or embarrassing truths, as when we say that a dead person passed away or a celebrity who has canceled an appearance is suffering from exhaustion. You'll have to utilize so-called white lies on a regular basis to disguise unpleasant realities (more or less) smoothly. We employ euphemisms like these to keep the issue under control, mostly to avoid emotional outbursts. For example, we frequently say "before I depart" rather than "before I die," which has a more soothing sense. It's a common language solution that may be found in both regular interactions and literary works [8].

2. Indirection: A euphemism may replace an explicit description of an action, as when people speak of going to the bathroom or of others sleeping together.

3. Litotes: Sometimes, euphemism occurs in the form of this rhetorical device in which the gravity or force of an idea is softened or minimized by a double negative, as in the reference to someone as being not unattractive. Litotes is a figure of speech that uses understatements to emphasize the exact opposite of the actual situation. It is one of the writers' favourites [3]. Despite its complexity, litotes is simple to explain using examples: not particularly brilliant – dumb; not a prom queen – ugly; not bad at all – fantastic. It's all about the irony in this case because the writers aren't trying to make fun of anything. The new detail will scarcely go ignored by Litotes.

4. Mispronunciation: Alteration of pronunciation is a form of euphemism, as when we say *frigging* or *shoot*, or *jeez* or *cripes*, so as not to offend people by using profanity (figurative or literal). These types of euphemisms, involving rhyme, alliteration, or shortening, are also called minced oaths.

5. Modification: A bluntly offensive noun can be transformed into a euphemism by converting it to an adjective, as in saying someone has socialist leanings rather than labeling them a socialist outright.

6. Personification: One form of euphemism is when things that some people prefer not to mention candidly, such as genitals, are assigned personal names. (I will go beyond euphemism and let readers think of examples on their own.)

7. Slang: Much of slang, derived to produce a vocabulary exclusive to a social group, is euphemism, as in the use of *joint* for *marijuana* (itself a slang term, derived from the Spanish names Mary and Juana — closely related to “Mary Jane,” yet another euphemism) [7].

8. Politeness: Impoliteness is commonly viewed as a social taboo, which is why euphemisms are used to mitigate the severity of a situation. Politeness is a conversational construct that reduces the frequency of improper language answers. It is regarded as a matter of good manners and serves to make all parties involved in the conversation more comfortable and spontaneous.

9. Diplomacy: Diplomatic debate is a true art form. Negotiation skills, anxiety, and strategic thinking are all required as well as euphemisms. It’s easy to see why euphemisms deserve such a prominent place in politics, given their role as acceptable substitutes for potentially divisive words or phrases. Diplomacy is the art of telling someone to go to hell in such a way that they ask for directions, as Winston Churchill put it. In order to succeed in this field, you must learn to utilize words in new ways, giving them new meanings in the context of international politics. It’s almost as if you can speak another language, which is why authors should study it as well.

10. Spin Euphemism : If you work in public relations, you should be familiar with spin euphemisms. These are used to create profit-generating confusion, confuse consumers, or sway public opinion. Spin is probably the most dangerous type of euphemism, but it is certainly not the least common. It is frequently used by politicians and corporations. It minimizes unwanted repercussions by downplaying the negative characteristics of a product, idea, or event. When it comes to firing people, for example, firms frequently use the term “rationalization.” It is not, however, strictly tied to economics or politics; individuals all around you utilize it all the time. When trying to persuade a publisher that his or her new book is fantastic, say something like, “There is currently no other book that covers what my book covers” or something like. That is correct, but a meaningless spin [8].

CONCLUSION

There are things in everyday life that people don't want to talk directly about, so they will continue to use euphemisms, even creating others, along with those who have a tradition, because people will not be able to communicate with each other as they wish, if only you do not create euphemisms. Therefore, the idea that euphemisms, as well as the language of taboos, belonged only to the world of uncivilized or periods before modern civilization, is unacceptable, while we see that even in modern Europe aimed at removing forbidden words, is still widely used.

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